

Using Some Linear Dynamic Systems with Bivariate Wavelets

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ABSTRACT

Some linear dynamic systems, represented by Autoregressive with exogenous input variables (ARX models), were used to forecast crude oil prices (considered as dependent variable or output variable) for OPEC organization with the help of crude oil production (considered as independent variable or input variable) for the same organization depending on the data started from the period of 1973 until 2018.

First, the data were processed and analyzed through some statistical packages, such as MATLAB & SIMULINK R2018b, SPSS v25, EasyFit v5.5, and Microsoft Excel 2016. Using classical ARX method and proposed method (Bivariate Wavelet

Filtering) for the time series data in order to select one of them for forecasting through comparing three measures of accuracy, MSE, FPE, and AIC. Then, applying crude oil prices for OPEC using the classical ARX models and ARX models with applying the bivariate wavelet filtering, especially bivariate Haar wavelet.

The main conclusions of the thesis were that the success of proposed model in forecasting of crude oil prices using bivariate wavelet filtering was more appropriate than classical models, ARX models have more forecasting parameter options than ARIMA models with the impact of input variable on output variable, and the forecasting of crude oil prices using proposed method in 2019 and 2020.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Meaning
ACF	Autocorrelation Function
ADF	Augmented Dickey Fuller test
AIC	Akaike's Information Criterion
AR	Autoregressive
ARARX	Autoregressive Autoregressive with exogenous input Variable
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
ARMA	Autoregressive Moving Average
ARMAX	Autoregressive Moving Average with Exogenous input
ARX	Autoregressive with exogenous input Variable
CCF	Cross-Correlation Function
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DWT	Discrete Wavelet Transform
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
FPE	Final Prediction Error
LDS	Linear Dynamic Systems
MA	Moving Average
MSE	Mean Square Error
OE	Output Error
OPEC	Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries
PACF	Partial Autocorrelation Function
SIT	System Identification Toolbox
USD	United States Dollar
WTI	West Texas Intermediate

CHAPTER ONE
(INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW)

CHAPTER ONE

4.1 Introduction

An important field of Statistics is Time Series Analysis which could be used many other scientific fields in order to make future planning and management for governmental and nongovernmental institutions. It deals with the methods and theory involved in analyzing datasets which is collected over time and helping to understand the past behavior of phenomena. It can be used for compare between two or more times series concerning the type of growth, for instance growth in crude oil prices, consumption of a product, etc.

Forecasting of Linearly time series analysis is a famous developed method that the researchers using in their forecast, but in the actual world most of data systems are nonlinear, which demonstrates itself in a much larger extents of possible dynamical behaviors (Brockwell & Davis, 2016). Also, it is clear that models based on the time series only, without taking any related input variable into consideration, could not be accurate. Therefore, more accurate models are taken by integrating exogenous input variables into the model which is called Linear Dynamic Systems (Nelles, 2001; Ali, 2022).

The linear dynamic systems (LDS) model is the most commonly used in time series model for economic, engineering, financial, and medical applications because of its respective simplicity, mathematically predictable behavior, inference, and predictions could be done effectively for the models. It is possible to identify LDS models using *parametric* and *nonparametric* models, and both are divided into *time domain* models and *frequency domain* models. Time domain models consist of *equation error* models and *output error* models. Equation error models are the thesis's goal, because it contains ARX models. Thus, the equation error models divided into ARX, ARMAX, and ARARX (Nelles, 2001; Saaed, 2015; أبو ليدة، 2017; Mustafa & Ali, 2013; Ali et al. 2023).

The ARX models can be utilized to enhance the forecasting of output series (Y), though applying the past data of both the Y series and the exogenous input series (X). That is especially right if the input series is an important indicator (Wei, 2006; Ali et al. 2022; Shahla et al. 2023).

In the human beings' life, data are used to deal with daily works in any field and very important to organize their life, but analyzing and forecasting of these data need some processing such as denoising in order to reduce contamination through using many filtering methods, such as wavelet filtering transform. The wavelet transform is a new mathematical tool developed mainly since the middle of the 1980's (Sheng, 2000). First time for using wavelets were in geophysics for analyzing data in seismic surveys that are used in oil and mineral exploration in order to get pictures of layering in subsurface rock. Geophysicists rediscovered them; mathematicians had developed them to solve abstract problems some 30 years earlier, but had not anticipated their applications in signal processing (Boggess & Narcowich, 2009; Ali & Jwana, 2022; Ali & Saleh, 2022).

There are many types of wavelet transforms such as Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT), Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), Fast Wavelet Transform, etc. The DWT has many attractive qualities that make it a good method for time series, displaying features that change in both time and frequency. Haar Wavelet is one of the DWT that is used first by its creator Alfred Haar in 1910.

The great importance of this thesis is that many institutions and organizations headed by OPEC Organization, governmental bodies and private bodies, ministry of planning, ministry of finance and economy can benefit from it, and use it as the basis of future strategic plans.

Since this thesis trying to understand and forecast the crude oil prices in OPEC Organization, and data had been collected from secondary sources, the applied thesis (Quantitative Thesis) is being taken into consideration. The ARX models has been used

to analyze and forecast the prices of OPEC crude oil because it is one of the biggest issues for governments in the Middle East countries (Ali & Saleh, 2021).

This thesis is organized into four chapters. Chapter one is the introduction and literature review. It deals with the statement of the problem, objective of the study, thesis importance, methodology, and literature review. The second chapter presents theoretical part of the thesis which is the review of time series models, linear dynamic systems, ARX models, and bivariate wavelets. Chapter three dedicated for practical part in order to gain the most important results concerning the forecasting of crude oil prices using time series analyses. Finally, conclusion and recommendations are in chapter four.

4.2 Thesis Objectives

The main objectives of this thesis are forecasting of yearly crude oil prices for OPEC Organization using traditional and proposed methods, and comparison between these two methods in order to obtain the best model using statistical measurements. So, in the proposed method the researcher will try to denoise contaminated data using bivariate wavelet filtering in the estimation of some linear dynamic systems.

4.3 Thesis Literature Reviews

Now, it is time to explore what researches have already been done on this topic according to the time period.

Many researchers have been working on the ARIMAX models in many disciplines and worked on wavelet transformation in order to develop the time series analysis and reduce noising in time series data.

First wavelet filter was introduced by the Hungarian mathematician Alfred Haar in 1909 – 1910 (Haar, 1910). The Haar wavelet is one of the earliest examples of what is known now as a compact, dyadic, orthonormal wavelet transform. Many groups of researchers were worked independently on Haar's basis function in 1930s. A physicist called Paul Levy investigated Brownian motion (a type of random signal). He found the

Haar basis function was better than Fourier basis functions for studying small complicated details in the Brownian motion (Burrus, et al., 1998; Ali et al. Saleh 2018).

In 1980s the early work in wavelets happened in France and USA by Grossmann, Morlet, Mallat, Meyer, Daubechies, and others, attracted the attention of the larger scientists who worked in the field of applied mathematics and statistics. So, statisticians started their researches on wavelets in the early of 1990s (Darilmaz, 2006).

Whitcher (1998) presented his PhD dissertation used DWT to assess nonstationarity in times series, and he tried to provide a more thorough investigation of ideas from the study of long memory processes change point detection and the ability of the DWT to approximately decorrelate time series on a scale by scale basis.

Fernndez & Olmeda (2000) analyzed the potential advantages of wavelet shrinkage methods for financial time series prediction and identification the best combination of parameters. Their approach consisted in applying wavelet shrinkage methods to obtain a "clean" signal, which is then used to estimate several linear models.

Lim & Lye (2004) worked on wavelet analysis of tide-affected low streamflows series in the time-scale domain. Their case study was a streamflow series observed at Kapit river in Malaysia and they provided conclusive evidence of the effect of tides at the flow-gauging site during the low flow period.

Conejo et al. (2005) proposed a wavelet-ARIMA technique, which consists of decomposing the price series using a discrete wavelet transform (DWT), then modeling the resulting detail and approximation series using ARIMA processes to obtain 24 hourly predicted values, and finally applying the inverse wavelet transform, to yield the predicted prices for the next 24 h. The performance of the wavelet-ARIMA technique was generally better than that of a standard ARIMA process.

مطر & حسين (2006) used dynamic models for the transfer function with multi-inputs because more effective inputs give better results. They compared Black Box models

such as ARX, ARMAX, BJ, OE, and appeared that best model was "BJ" model depending a group of statistical and geometrical standards.

عبدالله & الجواد (2007) studied wavelet characteristics for the sunspot time series through using continuous wavelet analysis and the periodogram in it is marked primarily. The main results were irregularity in the length of wavelet period and also there was a clear shifting for these periods.

Percival (2008) applied DWT in the analysis of geophysical time series. He discussed the strengths and weaknesses of the maximal overlap DWT, orthonormal DWT, and the continuous wavelet transform to transform a time series into coefficients describing how the series varies over particular scales.

الزبيدي (2009) in his dissertation compared wavelets with Wiener and Kalman filtering in analyzing time series models represented by autoregressive models of first order AR(1). Also, he used DWT with some kinds of thresholding as an input for Artificial Neural Networks depending on simulation experiments and applying them on real data.

عبدالمجيد & حياوي (2009) compared between the prediction of state space models and stochastic dynamic linear systems, and found that forecasting through dynamic linear system models are the best because they gave minimum statistical criteria.

الصفراوي et al. (2010) proposed method to shrink the wavelet to deal with the problem of noise that may facing time series data, and trying to find the best estimation of the of the autoregressive model parameters of order (p). They applied annual rainfall in Erbil city for the period (1992-2007) in order to use the proposed method.

عبدالقادر (2011) worked on comparing Box-Jenkins models before and after applying wavelet filtering in order to reduce the order of the models due to noise reduction in the data.

Al-Wadia (2011) showed the advantage of wavelet transforms in forecasting financial time series data, and used Amman stock market data as a tool to show the

ability of wavelet transform in forecasting financial time series. They suggested a technique for forecasting the financial time series data, based on Wavelet transforms and ARIMA model.

Cerny (2016) discussed the analyzing and forecasting of hourly and daily electricity price on the deregulated Czech daily electricity market. He used for daily price data the redundant Haar Wavelet Transform decomposition of the time series in combination with ARIMA and Neural Networks models for forecasting, and for hourly data, ARIMA and Neural Network models use used.

شعبيّة & جمعة (2017) worked on ARX and ARIMAX models to forecast daily drinking water filtering using water erosion measurement for Al-Karkh project in Baghdad governorate for 3 months.

مسلم & صابر (2018) Compared some wavelet estimators for parameters in the linear regression model with errors follows Autoregressive Fractionally Integrated Moving Average (ARFIMA) model. They proved that Wavelet Generalized Maximum Likelihood (WML) was the most reliable and efficient from the other estimators, also the results indicated that changing of fractional difference parameter (d) does not impact on the results.

In this thesis, applying two forecasting methods represented by classical and researcher's proposed methods on real data for forecasting yearly crude oil prices with helping of input exogenous time series variable represented by crude oil production for Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC).

CHAPTER TWO
(THEORETICAL PART)

CHAPTER TWO

5.1 Introduction

The theoretical part is important because it will be the viewfinder through which researchers evaluate their thesis problems and thesis questions. Its required for quantitative studies to know which information should include in the study thesis. In this chapter, time series analysis will be discussed with dynamic system models including ARX models and then bivariate wavelet also will be discussed. So, this chapter describes theories and models that will be applied in practical chapter of the thesis.

5.2 Time Series Analysis

One of the most important fields of future estimation is time series, it is a data collection recorded over a period of time such as weekly, monthly, quarterly, or yearly. An analysis of history "a time series" can be used by administration to make present decisions and plans depending on long-term forecasting. Usually a researcher can assume that past patterns will continue into the future (Cryer & Chan, 2008).

5.2.1 Time Series Components

There are four main components to a time series which are:

1. **Trend Component:** A time series may be stationary or exhibit trend over time. Long term trend is typically modeled as a linear, quadratic or exponential function.
2. **Seasonal Component:** When a repetitive pattern is observed over some time horizon, the series is said to have seasonal behavior. Seasonal effects are usually associated with calendar or climatic changes. Seasonal variation is frequently tied to yearly cycles.
3. **Cyclical Component:** An upturn or downturn not tied to seasonal variation. Usually results from changes in economic conditions.

4. Irregular Component (Random error): Everything else (Makridakis, et al., 1998).

A. Additive Model:

A common approach to modeling time series data (Y) in which it is assumed that the four components of a time series; *trend component* (T), *seasonal component* (S), *cyclical component* (C) and *irregular component* (I), are added to form the values of the time series at each time period (see eq. 2.1).

$$y_t = T_t + S_t + C_t + I_t \dots \quad (2.1)$$

Where: $t = 1, 2, \dots, n$

y_t = Data at period t .

T_t = Trend component at period t .

S_t = Seasonal component at period t .

C_t = Cyclic component at period t .

I_t = Irregular (Random Error) component at period t .

B. Multiplicative Model:

In this model, the time series consists of multiplying the four components (see eq. 2.2). this model is suitable if the seasonal variations decrease or increase proportionally with decreases and increases in the level of the trend.

$$y_t = T_t \times S_t \times C_t \times I_t \dots \quad (2.2)$$

It is possible to take logarithm of the above equation and the model will be transformed to additive model.

5.2.2 Time Series Forecasting

Since ever Human beings desire to know the future of their plans and businesses but unfortunately, they could not do that properly because of lack of good techniques for forecasting and lack of fast computerized machines. Nowadays, under present

technology and globalization, forecasting represents as an important tool to solve many problems in different fields, such as business, industry, government, social science, economics, politics, medicine, environmental sciences, etc.

Sometimes forecasting through univariate time series models will not give good estimates for future value, therefore, it will be possible to use dynamic models (multiple time series models) that represented by output series (dependent variable) and using one or more input series (independent variable). For instance, crude oil sales may be related to oil productions and demands or monthly electricity consumption series may have relation with temperature and humidity. These models are called Transferred function models (Black-Box models) and have other names such as interrupted time series models, intervention models, and Box-Tiao models (Wei, 2006; Ali et al. 2018).

5.2.3 Some Important Definitions

A. Data Processing: When a time series is not stationary around mean, the best way to make it stationary is taking first or second order differences for the series. Stabilizing the mean of a time series could be by removing changes in the level of a time series, and therefore reducing trend and seasonality. Computing the differences between successive observations is called differencing, it can be computed by the following first difference equation (Mills, 2019; Ali et al. 2019):

$$z_t = \nabla y_t = y_t - y_{t-1} = (1 - B)y_t \quad \dots (2.3)$$

where z_t is the difference between two consecutive observations (first order difference), and ∇ is a difference (backward) operator and B is called a backshift operator, it means that $\nabla = (1 - B)$.

The second order difference could be easily written through equation (2.4) in the following manner.

$$\begin{aligned} z_t &= \nabla^2 y_t = \nabla y_t - \nabla y_{t-1} = y_t - 2y_{t-1} + y_{t-2} \\ \Rightarrow z_t &= (1 - 2B + B^2)y_t = (1 - B)^2 y_t \quad \dots (2.4) \end{aligned}$$

Practically, to transform any non-stationary time series to stationary it is seldom needed to go beyond second order differencing (Bisgaard & Kulahci, 2011; Montgomery, et al., 2015; Palma, 2016; Ali 2017; Ali et al. 2021).

In case of taking seasonal differences, the difference will be between an observation and the corresponding observation from the previous year (or quarter, month, etc. (Omar et al, 2020; Ali 2018).

$$z_t = y_t - y_{t-k} = (1 - B^k)y_t \quad \dots (2.5)$$

where, lag k is the seasonal difference could be 4, 6, 12.

There is another way to transform a nonstationary series to stationary which is called Detrending. The detrended series is obtained by removing the regression part from the series y_t , its formula is as follows (Palma, 2016; Ali et al. 2023):

$$e_t = y_t - \hat{B}_0 - \hat{B}_1 x_{1t} - \dots - \hat{B}_p x_{pt} \quad \dots (2.6)$$

After that, the methods of time series can be applied to this new series (error series).

B. Stationary Time Series: It is a series that has no systematic variation in mean, i.e. no trend, and at the same time there is no systematic variations in the variance. In another way, the properties a data section are much like those of any other section and do not depend on time. For example, any product that its sales do not fluctuated increasingly or decreasingly over time is called stationary around mean, and the variance around mean will stay unchangeable over time (Makridakis, et al., 1998; Chatfield, 2004). Hence, A time series is stationary when its properties do not depend on the time at which the series is observed (no trend and not seasonality). But when we observe cyclic behaviors with no trend or seasonality, the series will be stationary. The reason of this situation is that because the cycles are not of a fixed length (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2019).

C. Strictly and Weakly stationary Time Series: A strictly stationary time series is provided when the joint distribution of $(y_{t_1}, y_{t_2}, \dots, y_{t_m})$ has the same distribution as $(y_{t_1+h}, y_{t_1+h}, \dots, y_{t_m+h})$ for all h , where m is an arbitrary positive integer and (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m) is a collection of m positive integers. A weakly stationary is provided when both the mean of y_t and the covariance between y_t and y_{t-k} are time invariant, where k is an arbitrary integer. Therefore, more concretely y_t is weakly stationary time series when it has a constant mean and a covariance that does not depends on time (Tsay, 2010; Ali et al. 2023):

$$\text{➤ } E(y_t) = \mu, \text{ which is a constant,}$$

$$\text{➤ } Cov(y_t, y_{t-k}) = \gamma_k, \text{ which only depends on } k.$$

➤ **D. Test of Stationary:** One of the famous tests of stationary is Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF), it is also known as unit root tests to specify the stationary of a time series. This test is trying to test the following hypothesis (Palma, 2016; Raza et al. 2018):

H_0 : The time series has a unit root (Non-stationary)

H_1 : The time series does not have a unit root (Stationary)

The ADF t-statistics is given by the following equation:

$$t = \frac{\hat{\phi}-1}{\hat{\sigma}_\phi} \dots (2.7)$$

where:

$$\hat{\phi} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n y_t y_{t-1}}{\sum_{t=1}^n y_{t-1}^2} \text{ and } \hat{\sigma}_\phi = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{\phi} y_{t-1})^2}{n-1}$$

According to ADF result test, if the hypothesis is rejected, then the series is stationary and vice versa.

E. Autocorrelation and Partial Autocorrelation Functions (ACF & PACF): The ACF and PACF of a time series are very useful when showing them in their graphical forms. The ideas behind these two measurements are detecting non-randomness in the time series data and determining a suitable model if the data are not random. They provide a helpful check for seasonality, cycles, and other time series patterns. The following are ACF and PACF formulas (Pankratz, 1983; Makridakis, et al., 1998):

$$\rho_k = \frac{E(y_{t-\mu})(y_{t-k-\mu})}{\sqrt{E(y_{t-\mu})^2 E(y_{t-k-\mu})^2}} = \frac{E(y_{t-\mu})(y_{t-k-\mu})}{E(y_{t-\mu})^2} \dots (2.8)$$

since, for a stationary process, the variance at time t is the same as at time $t-k$ (or $t+k$). Then the ACF at lag k (the correlation between y_t and y_{t-k}) is as follows:

$$\rho_k = \frac{\gamma_k}{\gamma_0} \dots (2.9)$$

Autocorrelation function in time series analysis is very important, especially in ARIMA models because these models aim to describe the autocorrelations in the data.

F. Cross-Correlation Function (CCF): It is an adequate measure of the strength and direction of correlation between two variables (Output and input variables – Y , X variables). It can be saying that x_t and y_t are jointly stationary if they are both univariate stationary processes and the cross-covariance function between x_t and y_t could be written as follows (Wei, 2006; Ali & Qais 2016):

$$\gamma_{xy}(k) = Cov(x_t, y_{t-k}) = E(x_t - \mu_x)(y_{t-k} - \mu_y), \quad \text{for } k = 0, \mp 1, \mp 2, \dots$$

Then the CCF could be written as follows:

$$\rho_{xy}(k) = \frac{\gamma_{xy}(k)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \dots (2.10)$$

For a good model, the cross-correlation function between residuals of the model and input variable does not go significantly outside the confidence region (Ljung, 1999).

G. Forecasting Accuracy: The accuracy of forecasting is a measure, which shows the efficiency of forecasting model. There are many options of calculating the measurements of forecasting error. Each one is a little bit different information. First, it

is important to find the forecasting error. It is a deviation of actual value and predicted value: $e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t \dots (2.11)$

Then, it could be finding the following criteria (Ljung, 1999; Burnham & Anderson, 2002; Bisgaard & Kulahci, 2011; Jönsson, 2015; Brockwell & Davis, 2016):

❖ Mean Square Error (MSE): $MSE = \hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2}{n} \dots (2.12)$

❖ Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE):

$$MAPE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t|}{ny_t} * 100 \dots (2.13)$$

❖ Mean absolute error (MAE): $MAE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n |y_t - \hat{y}_t|}{n} \dots (2.14)$

❖ Final Prediction Error (FPE): $FPE = \frac{n+p}{n-p} \hat{\sigma}_e^2 \dots (2.15)$

❖ Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC): $AIC = n \ln(\hat{\sigma}_e^2) + 2p \dots (2.16)$

Where:

$\hat{\sigma}_e^2$: maximum likelihood estimate of the residual variance $\hat{\sigma}_e^2$;

p : number of estimated parameters in the model including a possible constant term.

❖ Fitting Criterion: $Fit = \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^n (y_t - \bar{y}_t)^2}} \right) * 100 \dots (2.17)$

Models with smallest criteria are preferable for all the above except fitting model criterion.

5.3 ARIMA Modelling and Forecasting

ARIMA models are approaches of time series modelling and famous by Box-Jenkins approaches according to the name of scientists who created and developed them in 1976. A good ARIMA model requires as a minimum 45 observations and a reasonably large sample size is required for a seasonal time series (Pankratz, 1983).

The Box-Jenkins model is a combination of the AR and MA models. It assumes that the time series is stationary. Box and Jenkins recommend differencing nonstationary series one or more times to achieve stationarity. Doing so produces an ARIMA model, with the "I" standing for "Integrated". Some formulations transform the series by

subtracting the mean of the series from each data point. This yields a series with a mean of zero. Whether you need to do this or not is dependent on the software you use to estimate the model. Box-Jenkins models can be extended to include seasonal autoregressive and seasonal moving average terms. Although this complicates the notation and mathematics of the model, the underlying concepts for seasonal autoregressive and seasonal moving average terms are similar to the non-seasonal autoregressive and moving average terms. The most general Box-Jenkins model includes difference operators, autoregressive terms, moving average terms, seasonal difference operators, seasonal autoregressive terms, and seasonal moving average terms. As with modeling in general, however, only necessary terms should be included in the model (Hamilton, 1994; Montgomery, et al., 2015; Kareem et al. 2020).

Now, the Autoregressive models of order p (AR(p)), could be written as follows (Hamilton, 1994; Montgomery, et al., 2015):

$$y_t = \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t \quad \dots (2.18)$$

where p is a nonnegative integer, $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p$ are model parameters to be estimated, and ϵ_t is a series of random errors each with mean equal 0 and constant variance equals σ^2 ($\epsilon_t \sim iid Normal(0, \sigma^2)$).

Then, using backshift operators, AR(p) in 2.18 could be written as follows:

$$\phi(B)y_t = \epsilon_t \dots (2.19)$$

or it can be written in the following way:

$$y_t = \frac{1}{\phi(B)} \epsilon_t \dots (2.20)$$

where: $\phi(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p$

Concerning the moving average models of order q (MA(q)), could be written as follows (Hamilton, 1994; Montgomery, et al., 2015):

$$y_t = \epsilon_t - \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \quad \dots (2.21)$$

where q is a nonnegative integer, $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$ are model parameters to be estimated, and ϵ_t is a series of random errors each with mean equal 0 and constant variance equals σ^2 . Then, using backshift operators, MA(q) in Equation 2.21 could be written as follows:

$$y_t = \theta(B) \epsilon_t \dots (2.22)$$

where: $\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$

Depending on Equation 2.18 and 2.21, it can be combine the two models (AP(p) and MA(q)) in one equation and the resulting model called Autoregressive Moving Average models of order p and q (ARMA(p,q)), as presented in the following equation (Mills, 2019):

$$y_t = \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t - \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \dots (2.23)$$

Using backshift operators, ARMA(p,q) in Equation 2.23 could be written as follows:

$$\phi(B)y_t = \theta(B) \epsilon_t \quad \text{Or} \quad y_t = \frac{\theta(B)}{\phi(B)} \epsilon_t \dots (2.24)$$

The above equation is for stationary time series, but if the time series does not have stationarity, then Equation 2.24 will be written in another way. Therefore, if the time series is nonstationary in mean, then difference should be taken in order to have stationary time series and the model will be called Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA(p,d,q)) process of order p , d , and q , as presented in the following equation:

$$(1 - B)^d y_t = \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t - \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \dots (2.25)$$

Using backshift operators, ARIMA(p,d,q) in Equation 2.25 could be written as follows:

$$\phi(B)(1 - B)^d y_t = \theta(B) \epsilon_t \dots (2.26)$$

The above model could be named Nonseasonal ARIMA because there are no seasonal effects in the time series. However, if the data has seasonality in it. Then, the time series data will be called Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA (p,d,q),(P,D,Q)^S) and

Equation 2.26 will be written as follows (Shumway & Stoffer, 2011; Brockwell & Davis, 2016; Ali, 2011; Ali & Awaz, 2017):

$$\phi^*(B^S)\phi(B)(1 - B^S)^D(1 - B)^d y_t = \theta^*(B^S)\theta(B) \epsilon_t \dots (2.27)$$

where D is a seasonal difference, S is the number of periods or the number of observations per season (week, month, quarter, years, etc.) or the number of lags, and $\phi^*(B^S) = 1 - \phi_1 B^S - \phi_2 B^{2S} - \dots - \phi_p B^{pS}$, and $\theta^*(B^S) = 1 - \theta_1 B^S - \theta_2 B^{2S} - \dots - \theta_q B^{qS}$

5.4 Linear Dynamic Systems (LDS)

These types of models are the most common, it is also known as Black Box models. In general, the models of LDS are expansion of the time series models by adding the input variable (x) to them, as in Figure 2.1 shown, because the time series models are usually not accurate, and divided LDS models into two parts, as shown in Figure 2.2 (Andersen, 1997; Nelles, 2001; Isermann & Münchhof, 2010; الشرايبي، 2017).

Figure (2.1): Dynamic System with Input x_t , Output y_t and Disturbance ϵ_t

Figure (2.2): Classification of Linear Models according to Equation Error and Output Error Models

5.4.1 Equation Error Models

This type includes ARX and ARMAX models, are characterized by the existence of a polynomial order $\Phi(B)$ as the dynamic denominator of the input transform function and the noise transform function. This is in line with the fact that noise does not affect directly on the output of the model, but instead enters the model before the $\frac{1}{\Phi(B)}$ filter, where $\Phi(B)$ is presented in Equation 2.20 (Ljung, 1999; & جمعة شعيب، 2017; Ali et al. 2018; Ali et al. 2016).

a) Autoregressive with exogenous input (ARX) model

This model represents the simple relationship between the input and output, see Figure 2.3, provided by the linear difference Equation 2.28, which is also sometimes called the equation error model due to its description of white noise as a discrete error (Ljung, 1999; Saaed, 2015; جمعة & شعيب، 2017; Ali & Esraa, 2016; Ali et al. 2017):

$$y_t = \frac{\Psi(B)}{\Phi(B)} x_t + \frac{1}{\Phi(B)} \epsilon_t \dots (2.28)$$

where $\Psi(B)$ and $\phi(B)$ are the transfer functions of the deterministic part and the stochastic part, respectively and x_t is the input signal, y_t is the output signal, and ϵ_t is the white noise (equation error).

Thus, Equation 2.28 could be rewritten as shown below:

$$\phi(B)y_t = \Psi(B)x_t + \epsilon_t \dots (2.29)$$

$$\Rightarrow y_t - \phi_1 y_{t-1} - \phi_2 y_{t-2} - \dots - \phi_{na} y_{t-na} = \psi_1 x_{t-nk} + \psi_2 x_{t-nk-1} + \dots + \psi_{nb} x_{t-nk-nb+1} + \epsilon_t \dots (2.30)$$

The orders of the above model are **na** and **nb**, whereas **nk** is the model time delay.

By introducing B-notation, which is widely used in the system identification literature for the sake of compatibility with the classical definition of the **B** transform (Backshift Operator), the numerator and denominator of Equation 2.28 can be defined as the following polynomials (Ljung, 1999; Ali & Tara, 2010):

$$\phi(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_{na} B^{na}$$

and

$$\psi(B) = \psi_1 B^{nk} + \psi_2 B^{nk+1} + \dots + \psi_{nb} B^{nk+nb-1}$$

It is possible to forecast the output variable using the its previous observations, as presented in the following formula:

$$\hat{y}_t = \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_{na} y_{t-na} + \psi_1 x_{t-nk} + \psi_2 x_{t-nk-1} + \dots + \psi_{nb} x_{t-nk-nb+1} + \epsilon_t \dots (2.31)$$

Figure (2.3): ARX Model Structure (Nelles, 2001; Ljung, 2001)

It should be noted that the ‘AR’ part of ‘ARX’ denotes the autoregressive part $\phi(B)y_t$ while the letter ‘X’ denotes the extra input $\Psi(B)x_t$.

b) Autoregressive Moving Average with Exogenous input model (ARMAX)

The main problem with the ARX models is the limited scope for defining of the disturbance term. ARMAX models overcome this problem by defining the equation error as a Moving Average (MA) of the white noise in the ARX models (Roubal, 2009; Nelles, 2001; Ali & Tara, 2007; Ali & Mahmood, 2009). The ARMAX model is presented in Equation 2.32 and its flowchart is depicted in Figure 2.4.

$$y_t = \frac{\Psi(B)}{\Phi(B)} x_t + \frac{\Theta(B)}{\Phi(B)} \epsilon_t \dots (2.32)$$

where $\Psi(B)$, $\Phi(B)$ and $\Theta(B)$ are the transfer functions of the deterministic part and the stochastic part respectively, while x_t is the input variable, y_t is the output variable, and ϵ_t is the white noise (Saaed, 2015; Ali & Shaymaa, 2016; Ali, 2007).

The numerator and denominator of Equation 2.32 could be defined as the following polynomials (Wei, 2006) (Lee, 2010) (أبوليدة، 2017; Ali, 2003; Ali, 2004):

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(B) &= 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_{na} B^{na} \\ \Psi(B) &= \psi_1 B^{nk} + \psi_2 B^{nk+1} + \dots + \psi_{nb} B^{nk+nb-1} \\ \Theta(B) &= 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_{nc} B^{nc}\end{aligned}$$

where **na**, **nb** and **nc**, are the orders of model, whereas **nk** is the model time delay.

Figure (2.4): ARMAX Model Structure (Nelles, 2001; Ljung, 2001)

It is possible to rewrite Equation 2.32 in another way, and it is as follows (Ljung, 2001; Ali & Jalil, 1998, 2003):

$$\phi(B)y_t = \Psi(B)x_t + \theta(B)\epsilon_t \dots (2.33)$$

The above ARMAX model is the most general among the models, because it has some special cases (Nelles, 2001; الشرايبي, 2017; Ali et al. 2010; Ali & Kurdistan, 2010):

- 1) When $\Psi(B) = 0$ and $\theta(B) = 1$, AR model will be obtained.
- 2) When $\psi(B) = 0$ and $\phi(B) = 1$, MA model will be obtained.
- 3) When $\phi(B) = 1$ and $\theta(B) = 1$, Finite Impulse Response model will be obtained.
- 4) When $\theta(B) = 0$, ARX model will be obtained.
- 5) When $\Psi(B) = 0$, MA model will be obtained.

It is possible to model the equation error as an autoregressive in which case the gotten model will be called an ARARX model if the equation error was modeled using the AR approach (instead of an additional MA filter $\theta(B)$, it possesses an additional AR filter $\frac{1}{\phi^*(B)}$ of the disturbance), or an ARARMAX model if an ARMA approach was used (Nelles, 2001; Ali, 2007).

It is viable to forecast the output variable using its previous observations, as presented in the following formula:

$$\hat{y}_t = \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_{na} y_{t-na} + \psi_1 y_{t-nk} + \psi_2 y_{t-nk+1} + \dots + \psi_{nb} y_{t-nk-nb+1} + \epsilon_t - \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_{nc} \epsilon_{t-nc} \quad \dots (2.34)$$

5.4.2 Output Error Models

Output error models can be distinguished as a noising model that do not contain dynamic process. So that, it is supposed that the noising affects directly on output process. Therefore, the noising model is independent of the determined process model, or in another way, the transfer function of input variable is independent of transfer function for output variable. Output Error models are divided into 2 parts (الشرابي، 2017؛ (أبولبدة، 2017):

a) OE Model: In the previous two models (equation error model) structures, the polynomial $\Phi(B)$ was used as a common factor in the denominator for determining the transfer functions $\frac{\Psi(B)}{\Phi(B)}$ and $\frac{\theta(B)}{\Phi(B)}$. Conversely, in the OE model structure, these transfer functions are parameterized separately because it is more natural physically. The flowchart for this model is depicted in Figure 2.5. Let the relationship between the input and the output variables be given by the following linear difference equation:

$$y_t = \frac{\Psi(B)}{\Omega(B)} x_t + \epsilon_t \quad \dots (2.35)$$

Figure (2.5): OE Model Structure (Nelles, 2001; Ljung, 2001)

b) Box-Jenkins model: This type of model is an extension of the output error model in which the output error is described using an ARMA model (see Figure 2.6) and can be expressed in the following form:

$$y_t = \frac{\Psi(B)}{\Phi(B)} x_t + \frac{\theta(B)}{T(B)} \epsilon_t \dots (2.36)$$

where $\Psi(B)$, $\Phi(B)$, $\theta(B)$ and $T(B)$ are the transfer functions of the deterministic part and the stochastic part respectively, while x_t is the input variable, y_t is the output variable, and ϵ_t is the white noise

Figure (2.6): BJ Model Structure (Nelles, 2001; Ljung, 2001)

c) Finite Impulse Response (FIR): It is a moving average filtering of the input. Therefore, the model output (y_t) is a weighted sum of previous inputs (x_t), and it is represented as Output error models. Its formula was discussed in section 2.4.1 in ARMAX models (Nelles, 2001).

5.5 Wavelet Analysis

Wavelets become very useful when applied to many problems, including analysis of time series (in acoustics, geology, filtration and forecasting in meteorology and economics), effective data storage, especially images (computer graphics, image animation in movie industry). Lately, a very fast development of wavelet based data mining techniques may be observed (Percival & Walden, 2000). One of the duties of knowledge discovery preprocessing is noise reduction. The goal of this subprocess is to separate the noise from the signal and then to reduce or remove the noise. The definition of a noise stays unclear because for some physical processes, it is difficult to clearly define it. In this thesis, it is assumed that the goal of filtering is to change the input signal in such a manner that the values of a time series are changed but the characteristic of signal stays the way it was. Most commonly used methods consider statistical approach or involve Fourier transform (Kozłowski, 2004; YU, et al., 2001).

It is well known from Fourier theory that a signal can be expressed as the sum of a series of sines and cosines. This sum is also referred to as a Fourier expansion. The big disadvantage of a Fourier expansion is that, it has only frequency resolution and no time resolution. This means that although it might be possible to determine all the frequencies present in a signal, but cannot know when they are present. To solve this problem in the past decades, several solutions have been developed that are more or less able to represent a signal in the frequency and time domain at the same time (Valens, 1999).

Wavelet analysis offers an alternative to harmonic analysis of multivariate time series and is particularly useful when the amplitudes and periods of dominant cycles are time dependent. Wavelets can take in multiscale nonstationary information and minimize correlation and time dependency in data (Zhang, 2018).

There are two functions that play a primary role in wavelet analysis, they are the wavelet function ψ and the scaling function ϕ . These two functions generate a family of

functions that can be used to reconstruct a signal. To emphasize the "marriage" involved in building this "family", ϕ is sometimes called the "father wavelet", and ψ is indicated to the "mother wavelet" (Bogges & Narcowich, 2009).

The wavelet transforms or wavelet analysis is probably the most recent solution to overcome the shortcomings of the Fourier transform. In wavelet analysis the use of a fully scalable modulated window solves the signal-cutting problem. The window is shifted along the signal and for every position the spectrum is calculated. Then this process is repeated many times with a slightly shorter (or longer) window for every new cycle. In the end, the result will be a collection of time-frequency representations of the signal, all with different resolutions. Because of this collection of representations, we can speak of a multiresolution analysis. In the case of wavelets, normally do not speak about time-frequency representations but about time-scale representations, scale being in a way the opposite of frequency, because the term frequency is reserved for the Fourier transform (Kaiser, 2011).

5.5.1 Wavelet Properties

Wavelet is a small wave that grows and decays in limited time period instead of being a wave that goes on forever, such as sinusoidal waves which are determined on a whole time domain $(-\infty, \infty)$ as seen in Figure 2.7 (Percival & Walden, 2000; Kozłowski, 2005).

Figure (2.7): Difference between Wave and Wavelet (Chan, 1995)

Let ψ be a real function of a real variable ω which fulfills the following conditions (Kozłowski, 2005; الزبيدي، 2009):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi(\omega) d\omega = 0 \quad \dots (2.37)$$

and

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi^2(\omega) d\omega = 1 \quad \dots (2.38)$$

Condition (2.38) means that for any $0 < \varepsilon < 1$, there is an interval $(-T, T)$ such that (الزبيدي، 2009):

$$\int_{-T}^T \psi^2(\omega) d\omega > 1 - \varepsilon \quad \dots (2.39)$$

Equation 2.39 is meaning the following also:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{-T} \psi^2(\omega) d\omega + \int_T^{\infty} \psi^2(\omega) d\omega < \varepsilon \dots (2.40)$$

If ε is close to 0, it may be seen that only in an interval $(-T, T)$ corresponding to this ε values $\psi(\omega)$ are different than 0. Outside of this interval they must be equal to 0. Interval $(-T, T)$ is small compared to an interval $(-\infty, \infty)$, on which a whole function is determined. Equation 2.37 implies that if $\psi(\omega)$ has some positive values, it also has to have some negative ones (a function “waves”). Therefore Equations 2.37 and 2.38 introduce a concept of a wavelet (small wave).

There is another property of wavelets which is the admissibility condition and it is as follow (Sheng, 2000):

$$\int \frac{|\psi(\omega)|^2}{|\omega|} d\omega < +\infty \dots (2.41)$$

can be used to first analyze and then reconstruct a signal without loss of information. In (2.41) $\psi(\omega)$ stands for the Fourier transform of $\psi(t)$.

The admissibility condition implies that the Fourier transform of $\psi(t)$ vanishes at the zero frequency, i.e. $|\psi(\omega)|^2|_{\omega=0} = 0$

As can be seen from Equation 2.37 the wavelet transform of a one-dimensional function is two-dimensional; the wavelet transform of a two-dimensional function is four-dimensional. The time-bandwidth product of the wavelet transform is the square of the input signal and for most practical applications this is not a desirable property.

Therefore, one forces some additional conditions on the wavelet functions in order to make the wavelet transform decrease quickly with decreasing scale. These are the regularity conditions and they state that the wavelet function should have some smoothness and concentration in both time and frequency domains (Sheng, 2000).

5.5.2 Multiresolution Analysis

The wavelets' power obtained from applying of multiresolution. From looking at a signal by a small window, applying the idea that an enough small portion of the wave will be nearly a stationary wave, where Gabor in 1946 create a transformation to solve the problem of stationary wave and called it Gabor Transform or Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). Then, instead of examining whole signals through the same window, variant portions of the wave are viewed throughout different resolutions (or size windows). Signals with High frequency portion are using small windows to give good time resolution, whereas low frequency portions use a big window to obtain good frequency information. It is worth to say that the Windows have equal area in spite of the height and width may differ in the analysis of wavelet. Hence, as frequency resolution becomes bigger as the time resolution become smaller (Lees, 2002; Gencay, et al., 2002).

An alternative representation of the original time series is the Fourier transform, where it outlines information in the data as a frequency function and thus does not keep information in time. It is the reverse of how the original time series observed, where no information was provided about frequency resolution. Figure 2.8 shows that figure **a** and **b** compare and contrast frequency and time resolutions of a time series through the time-

frequency plane. While looking at time series in the time domain, there will be a complete time resolution and no frequency resolution. The reverse is right after executing the Fourier transform. This has been seen by a good partitioning in the frequency axis in Figure 2.8a and by a good partitioning of the time axis in Figure 2.8b (Gencay, et al., 2002; عبدالقادر، 2011).

Figure (2.8): Different Transforms Provided Different Resolutions of Time and Frequency (Gencay, et al., 2002)

Figure 2.8c shows the balanced resolution between time and frequency by applying the STFT, the resulting expansion is a function of two parameters, frequency and time shift. Whereas, Figure 2.8d represents the discrete wavelet transform adaptively partitions the time-frequency plane, whereas the frequency increases, time is more strongly separated across longer frequency ranges (Gencay, et al., 2002).

5.5.3 Types of Wavelet Transformations (WT)

There are different Wavelet types of transformations that are used to suit different practical applications, such as (Hubbard, 1996; عبدالقادر، 2011):

- Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT)
- Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT)
- Fast Wavelet Transform
- Wavelet Packet Transform
- Stationary Wavelet Transform

5.5.3.1 Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT)

The continuous wavelet transform is the sum over all time of scaled and shifted versions of the mother wavelet ψ . Calculating the CWT results in many coefficients W , which are functions of scale and transfer (Sheng, 2000; Gencay, et al., 2002):

$$W(\lambda, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_{\lambda, t}(\omega) X(\omega) d\omega \quad \dots (2.42)$$

$$\psi_{\lambda, t}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \psi\left(\frac{\omega - t}{\lambda}\right) \quad \dots (2.43)$$

where:

ω : Time.

λ : Scale parameter.

t : Transfer parameter or time parameter.

$\psi_{\lambda, t}(\omega)$: Mother wavelet (Wavelet function).

$X(\omega)$: Decomposed into a set of basis functions.

5.5.3.2 Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT)

One of the most important transforms that is used in wavelets is DWT. This kind of transform and its variants are applied in a wide variety of disciplines, such as geology, turbulence, atmospheric science, applied mathematics, etc. (Gencay, et al., 2002). Therefore, the researcher tried to provide a broad idea about this type of wavelet

transforms as an introduction of practical chapter of this thesis and using it with time series analysis because it is a basic tool required for time series studying through wavelets.

The difference between CWT and DWT is that the DWT is obtained by using a finite number of scales instead of making transform for all scales. Discrete wavelets are again formed from a mother wavelet, but with scale and shift in discrete steps. The DWT makes the connection between wavelets in the continuous time domain and “filter banks” in the discrete time domain in a multiresolution analysis framework. Mathematically, the difference between CWT and DWT is in the mother wavelets (ψ) presented in Equation 2.43, where t and λ will be transformed into $t = 2^j k$ and $\lambda = 2^j$ (Chui, 1992; Vidakovic, 1999):

$$\psi_{\lambda,t}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^j}} \psi\left(\frac{\omega - 2^j t}{2^j}\right) \quad \dots (2.44)$$

where:

j : Scale level parameter.

k : location parameter.

The DWT gives adequate information for the analysis and synthesis of a signal, but is advantageously, much more efficient. Discrete Wavelet analysis is computed using the concept of filter banks. Filters of different cut-off frequencies analyze the signal at different scales. Resolution is changed by the filtering; the scale is changed by upsampling and downsampling. If a signal is put through two filters: first one is a high-pass filter, high frequency information is kept, low frequency information is lost, and the second is a low pass filter, low frequency information is kept, high frequency information is lost, then, the signal is effectively decomposed into two parts, a detailed part (high frequency), and an approximation part (low frequency). The subsignal produced from the low filter will have a highest frequency equal to half that of the original. According to Nyquist sampling this change in frequency range means that only

half of the original samples need to be kept in order to perfectly reconstruct the signal. More specifically this means that upsampling can be used to remove every second sample. The scale has now been doubled. The resolution has also been changed, the filtering made the frequency resolution better, but reduced the time resolution (Lees, 2002).

The approximation subsignal can then be put through a filter bank, and this is repeated until the required level of decomposition has been reached, as presented in Figure 2.9 (Lees, 2002).

Figure (2.9): The Tree Diagram of the DWT Parameters for Three Levels

Generally, separating out better detail through the effects of filters when all the details are 'added' together, then the original signal should be reproduced. This decomposition is looking like the decomposition of ratio 87/7 into parts of increasing details, as below:

$$87 / 7 = 10 + 2 + 0.4 + 0.02 + 0.008 + 0.0005 + \dots$$

Then, the above detailed parts could be reconstructed to make 12.4285714285714 where the original number is an approximation of the ratio 87/7 (Hubbard, 1996; Lees, 2002).

There are many types of wavelets, such as Haar, Daubechies, Meyer, Koiflets, Morlet, Shannon, Franklin, etc. (Daubechies, 1992; Grossmann & Morlet, 1984). In the next section, the researcher will discuss only one kind of these wavelets which is called Haar wavelet, because of its simplicity and easiness by most researchers and compatibility with the data that used in practical part.

5.5.4 HAAR Wavelet

The Haar wavelet, being an odd rectangular pulse pair, is the simplest and oldest orthonormal wavelet with compact support (Stankovic & Falkowski, 2003). There are two functions that have great roles in this wavelet, they are Scale function (ϕ) and wavelet function or mother wavelet (ψ). The scale function could be defined as follows (Burrus, et al., 1998; Cheng, 2011; Morettin, et al., 2017; Debnath & Shah, 2017):

$$\phi(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq \omega < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \dots \quad (2.45)$$

whereas, the mother wavelet could be written as follows:

$$\psi^{(H)}(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq \omega < \frac{1}{2} \\ -1 & \frac{1}{2} \leq \omega < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \dots \quad (2.46)$$

The following figure shows the Scale function and wavelet function (mother wavelet) (Burrus, et al., 1998).

Figure (2.10): Haar Wavelet Type Describing Scaling Function and Mother Wavelet

The Haar wavelet has the following characteristics:

1. Compact Support
2. Orthogonal
3. Biorthogonal
4. Symmetric

As a result of wavelet transform, it could be obtaining a set of wavelet coefficients calculated at different levels (scales) and in a wide range of observation points. There are many ways of doing this, two most often applied are orthonormal DWT and its slightly modified version which preserves scales but calculates wavelets in more densely chosen observation points (Kozłowski, 2005).

5.5.5 Wavelet Shrinkage

One of the most explored signal smoothing or cutting method utilizing wavelets is Wave Shrink method. Most of the applications of wavelet shrinkage deal with a single run of a time series expressed in a regression fashion: data = signal + noise (Donoho & Johnstone, 1995; Morettin, et al., 2017). The method is composed of three main steps (Raimondo, 2002; Kozłowski, 2005):

- 1) Apply the discrete wavelet transform DWT: At the beginning observed time series is transformed into the wavelet space by DWT.
- 2) Shrink the wavelet coefficients towards zero: In step two wavelet coefficients are modified, reduced according to the selected shrinkage function and a given threshold value. To accomplish this, one of three shrinkage functions may usually be used to establish how to modify wavelet time series coefficient.
- 3) Inverse DWT is applied on wavelet coefficients and as a result smoothed original signal (with reduced noises) is derived.

Shrinkage functions are formulas that define a correction coefficient $\delta_\lambda(x)$, which is subtracted from the corresponding wavelet coefficient. Calculated correction is relevant (different from 0) for those wavelet values, which exceed a given threshold parameter λ (Kozłowski, 2005).

5.5.6 Threshold Level

Thresholding allows the data itself to decide which wavelet coefficients are significant. There are some types of thresholding, such as hard thresholding is a ‘keep’ or ‘kill’ rule that have discontinuous function, soft thresholding is a ‘shrink’ or ‘kill’ rule that have a continuous function. In addition to these two types, there are many others, such as semi-soft shrinkage (firm shrinkage), mid shrinkage, non-negative Garrote, etc. and as long as the shrinkage function preserves the sign ($sign(\delta_\lambda(x)) = sign(x)$), and shrinks the magnitude ($|\delta_\lambda(x)| \leq |x|$) one can expect a denoising effect (Antoniadis, 2007).

Mathematically wavelet coefficients are estimated using the following thresholding levels (Kozłowski, 2005):

A. Hard Shrinkage Function:

$$\delta_\lambda^H(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & |x| \leq \lambda \\ x & |x| > \lambda \end{cases} \dots (2.47)$$

Subtracting this correction reduces those wavelet coefficients of the wavelet time series, which exceed threshold value, to zero.

B. Soft Shrinkage Function:

$$\delta_{\lambda}^S(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & |x| \leq \lambda \\ x - \lambda & x > \lambda \\ x + \lambda & x < -\lambda \end{cases} \dots (2.48)$$

By subtracting δ_{λ}^S correction considered wavelet time series coefficients are reduced to λ for positive coefficients and to $-\lambda$ for negative ones.

C. Non-negative Garrote Shrinkage Function:

$$\delta_{\lambda}^{NN}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & |x| \leq \lambda \\ x - \frac{\lambda^2}{x} & |x| > \lambda \end{cases} \dots (2.49)$$

Results of δ_{λ}^{NN} function subtracted from wavelet time series coefficients modify them directing to zero in such a manner that the more a coefficient exceeds the threshold value the more it is reduced towards zero.

5.5.7 Estimating Threshold Value

The goal of Wave Shrink method is to correctly estimate λ parameter. It may be achieved in various ways; the researcher will discuss Minimax estimating approach (Kozłowski, 2005).

This approach is so called Minimax threshold solution task. It is defined by Equation 2.50 (Kozłowski, 2005):

$$= \left\{ \frac{R_{\lambda}(\theta)}{n^{-1} + \min(\theta^2, 1)} \right\} \dots (2.50)$$

where, $R_{\lambda}(\theta)$ is defined as:

$$R_{\lambda}(\theta) = E(\delta_{\lambda}(x) - \theta)^2 \dots (2.51)$$

and $x \sim N(\theta, 1)$

What follows is it is proposed that the signal is a distribution of normal with expected value θ and a standard deviation equal to 1. Solving this problem analytically requires, at least, altering signal so that it suits this assumed condition.

In the next chapter, all the previous theoretical subjects will be used and discussed in order to understand the nature of the data and how to make forecasts. The assumptions of the ARX models and bivariate wavelets are going to be checked, and then the raw data that are related to the crude oil prices for OPEC organization will be analyzed and forecast for future years.

CHAPTER THREE
(PRACTICAL PART)

CHAPTER THREE

6.1 Introduction

Nowadays, fluctuations of crude oil prices have great impacts on the budgets of OPEC exporting countries, therefore, it is a very important to find a best forecasting model to determine future prices for crude oil in order to create optimum plans for these countries to increase their economic growth. In another hand, attempting to determine the best forecasting ARX models with and without bivariate wavelet filtering for time series data.

This chapter will be divided into some sections that are related to data analysis for the comparison of the effects of bivariate wavelets on time series forecasting of the yearly crude oil prices for OPEC organization. Depending on the objectives that were referenced in the first chapter, linear dynamic systems had been used in this chapter to make the forecasts before and after treating of data contamination problem. The obtained data were processed and analyzed through some packages, such as MATLAB & SIMULINK R2018b, SPSS v25, EasyFit v5.4, and Microsoft Excel 2016.

6.2 Data collection and Information about OPEC

The yearly crude oil prices and production of OPEC organization countries have been extracted from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) organization that is working as an international agency for collecting, analyzing, and publishing worldwide energy information (EIA, 2019). The yearly time series for the prices and production starts from the period of 1973 to 2018. The yearly crude oil price is in US dollar per barrel (Dollar/d) and the yearly production is in million barrels per day (Mb/d) for all OPEC members together.

Crude Oil is one of the most important raw materials in the Middle East. Everyday people are using hundreds of things that are made from oil or gas, such as

petrol for automobiles, gas for cooking and heating, electric power supply, street pavement, clothes, etc. Therefore, the production and prices of crude oil products are considered as an essential economic and political information needed for governments and citizens nowadays in order to organize their plans and intentions for the future.

One of the most important organizations in the field of crude oil production and exporting is the OPEC. This organization is created at Baghdad city on September, 1960 with a total of 5 founding members (Iraq, Iran, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, and Venezuela). It is a permanent, intergovernmental Organization consists of the following countries¹:

1. Iraq (founding members – 1960)
2. Iran (founding members – 1960)
3. Kuwait (founding members – 1960)
4. Saudi Arabia (founding members – 1960)
5. Venezuela (founding members – 1960)
6. Libya (1962)
7. United Arab Emirates (1967)
8. Algeria (1969)
9. Nigeria (1971)
10. Ecuador (1973)
11. Angola (2007)
12. Gabon (1975)
13. Equatorial Guinea (2017)
14. Congo (2018).

The Purpose of establishing this organization is to merge oil policies among the members of these countries, so as to keep prices stable and steady supply of crude oil to importing countries (OPEC Organization, 2019).

¹ Qatar joined OPEC in 1961, but cancelled its membership in January 2019. Indonesia joined OPEC in 1962, deactivated its membership in 2009, reactivated it in 2016, again decided to deactivate it in 2016.

6.3 Data Presentation and Processing

The data that will be manipulated as a time series are consists of two variables which are production of crude oil of OPEC countries and its prices annually. The crude oil production will be considered as an exogenous (independent) variable and an input for the models at the same time, while, crude oil prices will be considered as a dependent variable and an output for the models at the same time.

Presentation of any time series data is very important at the beginning of time series analysis in order to discover its properties, such as trend, seasonality and cyclical fluctuations. Therefore, it is clear from the time series plot that the crude oil price and production data are not stationary, i.e. the data have trend and an overall fluctuation, as seen in figure 3.1. ADF test will be used to identify the stationary of these time series data depending on equation 2.7.

After observing the time series plot of the data, it is clear that they are not stationary. In order to be confident, it is better to use ADF test for determining whether the time series data is stationary or not, that is, the test of the following hypothesis:

H_0 : The time series has a unit root (Non-stationary)

H_1 : The time series does not have a unit root (Stationary)

Figure (3.1): Yearly Crude Oil Prices and Production of OPEC Organization (1973 – 2018)

Table 3.1 shows the ADF test results where the p-value of both variables is greater than 0.05, i.e. not rejecting of null hypothesis (None of the two variables are significant). Thus, the two time series are not stationary and should make transformation to convert them to stationary through differencing, detrending, or any other method.

Table (3.1): ADF test for stationary for Crude Oil Price and Production data of OPEC (before and after Detrending)

Time series	ADF test	
	P-value before Detrending	P-value after Detrending
Crude Oil Production (X)	0.785	0.0326
Crude Oil Prices (Y)	0.525	0.0300

Different kinds of transformation are used and at the end the best transformation method for the two time series to be stationary was detrending method. Detrending was used through equation 2.6. The ADF test was reused and reveals that the two variables are stationary because the p-values were less than 0.05, i.e. rejection of unit root hypothesis, as presented in table 3.1.

It is obvious from figure 3.2 that the 2 variables are stationary in spite of cyclic variations.

Figure (3.2): Detrended Yearly Crude Oil Prices and Production of OPEC Organization (1973 – 2018)

6.4 Model Identification and Fitting

6.4.1 ARX Model Identification without Bivariate Wavelet Filtering

In this stage of LDS, the researcher will try to identify best model and fitting it to the processed data using the System Identification Toolbox (SIT) in MATLAB. The following steps are taken into consideration to find the best model:

- 1) Normality testing of model's variables (Input and output variables) using EasyFit program.
- 2) The processed input and output data are entered to the SIT;
- 3) Selecting time domain data type for model identification;
- 4) Estimation of the parameters of polynomial model;
- 5) SIT will automatically select the order of the model (n_a , n_b , n_k) for ARX models;
- 6) Choosing the best model through the accuracy criteria, such as MSE, AIC, MAPE, etc. (Model Validation);
- 7) Finally, drawing ACF for model's errors and CCF for input variable and model's errors in order to validate the adequacy of the model and randomness of errors.
- 8) At the end, normality testing of model's errors using EasyFit program, as seen in the following flowchart (figure 3.3).

Figure (3.3): Flowchart of ARMAX Model Identification System

The above steps will be applied for ARX models without undertaking bivariate wavelets filtering of the datasets. In case of undertaking the data filtering, it will be conducted after the first step.

Table 3.2 shows the normality test for input variable (Crude oil production):

H₀: The Input Variable (Crude oil production) without Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The input variable (Crude oil production) without Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.2): Test of Normality for Input Variable without Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Anderson-Darling		Chi-Squared	
Statistic	0.11602		0.57521		2.3178	
P-Value	0.52771		Not Available		0.80365	
α	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	11.07	15.086
Reject H₀?	No	No	No	No	No	No

Using 3 goodness of fit tests: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Anderson-Darling test, and Chi-Squared test. It appears from all these tests that the input variable is distributed normally at $\alpha = 0.01$, i.e. could not reject null hypothesis.

Concerning the normality test for output variable (Crude oil price), which is seen in table 3.3:

H₀: The output variable (Crude oil price) without Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The output variable (Crude oil price) without Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.3): Test of Normality for Output Variable without Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Anderson-Darling		Chi-Squared	
Statistic	0.09968		0.78081		2.2506	
P-Value	0.71314		Not Available		0.68977	
α	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	9.4877	13.277

Reject H_0 ?	No	No	No	No	No	No
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It is obvious from table 3.3 that it is normally distributed at $\alpha = 0.01$, meaning do not rejecting null hypothesis.

Based on ARX model parameters and MATLAB’s SIT², from 1000 models, the system selected best-fit models according to the accuracy criteria and number of parameters (MATLAB will present best-fit models that the number of their parameters do not exceed 20), as presented in figure 3.4. The Bar that is highlighted on the plot in red colour indicates a type of best-fit criteria that minimizes the sum of the squares of the difference between the validation data output and the model output. The name of the parametric model contains the model type, poles numbers, zeros, and time delays. For instance, the ARX10106 model is an ARX model with $n_a = 10$, $n_b = 10$, and a delay of 6 samples.

Figure (3.4): Best ARX Models according to Accuracy Criteria and Number of Parameters

² For more information about SIT, see (Ljung, 2016)

Table 3.4 shows the best 10 ARX models according to accuracy criteria (AIC, FPE, MSE, Fitting)

Table (3.4): Best 10 ARX Models According to Accuracy Criteria

Models	AIC	FPE	MSE	Fitting
ARX(10, 10, 6)	353.18	163.00	34.32	70.22
ARX(10, 9, 6)	353.93	160.73	36.43	69.32
ARX(9, 9, 6)	362.13	182.48	47.49	64.97
ARX(10, 3, 8)	358.57	156.94	52.31	63.24
ARX(10, 2, 9)	356.91	149.31	52.70	63.10
ARX(9, 7, 6)	365.46	188.31	55.70	62.07
ARX(9, 8, 7)	368.88	206.81	57.45	61.48
ARX(9, 5, 6)	365.10	180.86	60.29	60.54
ARX(9, 6, 7)	369.75	203.20	63.86	59.38
ARX(9 2 9)	364.90	173.61	68.39	56.97

Based on the model identification results, seen in Table 3.4, best ARX model is ARX (10,10,6) with a fitting percentage criterion equals to 70.22%, MSE: 34.32, FPE: 163, and AIC: 353.18.

Therefore, after estimating the parameters of the ARX(10, 10, 6) model through MATLAB, it could be written as presented in the following formula:

$$\phi(B)y_t = \psi(B)x_t + \epsilon_t$$

where: $\phi(B) = 1 - 0.6312B + 0.2592B^2 - 0.0778B^3 + 0.4692B^4 - 0.3267B^5 - 0.5895B^6 + 0.3106B^7 - 0.0112B^8 + 0.4886B^9 + 0.4225B^{10}$

and

$$\psi(B) = 2.469B^6 + 0.7093B^7 - 0.7222B^8 - 4.703B^9 + 3.554B^{10} + 0.1538B^{11} + 1.073B^{12} - 1.051B^{13} + 1.204B^{14} + 1.052B^{15}$$

The above selected ARX model has a random residuals and uncorrelated residual values with the exogenous input variable, as presented in figure 3.4 and 3.5. It is clear from Figure 3.5 that the autocorrelation values within the confidence intervals, and also

Figure 3.6 describes the cross-correlation of these residuals with the input variable. Both correlations are within acceptable intervals.

Figure (3.5): Error's Autocorrelation for ARX(10, 10, 6) Model

Figure (3.6): Cross-Correlation Errors for ARX(10,10,6) Model with of Input Variable

Now, it is possible to test the error term for normality test, as seen in table 3.5:

H₀: The Errors without Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The Errors without Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.5): Test of Normality for Errors without Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)		
	Kolmogorov-	Anderson-	Chi-Squared

	Smirnov		Darling			
Statistic	0.14196		1.2632		12.68	
P-Value	0.28428		Not Available		0.01295	
α	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	9.4877	13.277
Reject H0?	No	No	No	No	Yes	No

Table 3.5 shows the normality test for it using 3 goodness of fit tests: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Anderson-Darling test, and Chi-Squared test. It appears from all these tests that the error is distributed normally at $\alpha = 0.01$.

6.4.2 ARX Model Identification with Bivariate Wavelet Filtering

After finding an appropriate ARX model for the time series data which is related to crude oil price for OPEC with the help of exogenous input variable (Crude oil production), the researcher will try to use a proposed method for cleaning contaminated data (Denoising data) through appropriate bivariate wavelet filters for the time series data using MATLAB, and then forecasting it.

Many bivariate wavelet filters are used for the stationary two datasets such as Haar wavelet, Discrete Meyer wavelet (demy), Daubechies wavelet, and Coiflets (coif) wavelet. At the same time, many Threshold levels are used with these wavelet methods, such as Fixed Form threshold, SURE Threshold, Cross-Validation, and Minimax threshold. Also, for each threshold level there are soft and hard thresholding rules. That is mean that more than 30 different combinations of bivariate wavelet filters are used on the two datasets, and then using ARX models on the filtered datasets (transformed data).

The most appropriate bivariate wavelet method is Haar wavelet method with fixed form thresholding level and soft thresholding rules, as shown in Figure 3.7.

Figure (3.7): Haar Bivariate Wavelets with fixed Form thresholding Level and Soft Rules

In order to start applying ARX models, the stationary test is used to be confident that the 2 datasets are still stationary, as seen in table 3.6 that describe the ADF test for crude oil price and production data of OPEC (after applying Haar wavelet).

Table (3.6): ADF test for Crude Oil Price and Production data of OPEC (after applying Haar wavelet)

Time series	ADF test
	P-value
Crude Oil Production (X)	0.0382
Crude Oil Prices (Y)	0.0375

The ADF test was used and reveals that the two datasets are stationary because the p-values were less than 0.05, i.e. rejection of unit root hypothesis, as presented in table 3.6.

Table 3.7 shows the normality test for input variable (Crude oil production) after undertaking wavelet filtering for it using 3 goodness of fit tests: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Anderson-Darling test, and Chi-Squared test.

H₀: The Input Variable (Crude oil production) with Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The input variable (Crude oil production) with Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.7): Test of Normality for Input Variable with Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Anderson-Darling		Chi-Squared	
Statistic	0.16247		1.5464		0.72915	
P-Value	0.15768		Not Available		0.94769	
A	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	9.4877	13.277
Reject H₀?	No	No	No	No	No	No

It appears from all above tests (table 3.7) that the input variable is distributed normally at $\alpha = 0.01$.

Concerning the normality test for output variable (Crude oil price), it is shown in table 3.8:

H₀: The output variable (Crude oil price) with Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The output variable (Crude oil price) with Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.8): Test of Normality for Output Variable with Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Anderson-Darling		Chi-Squared	
Statistic	0.21848		1.9288		8.6281	
P-Value	0.02082		Not Available		0.0711	
A	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	9.4877	13.277
Reject H₀?	Yes	No	No	No	No	No

It is obvious from table 3.8 that it is normally distributed at $\alpha = 0.01$, meaning do not rejecting null hypothesis.

As presented in figure 3.8 the Bar that is highlighted on the plot in red colour indicates a type of best-fit criteria that minimizes the sum of the squares of the difference between the validation data output and the model output.

Figure (3.8): Best ARX Models according to Accuracy Criteria and Number of Parameters after Bivariate Wavelet filtering

Table 3.9 shows the best ARX model according to accuracy criteria after bivariate wavelet filtering (AIC, FPE, MSE, Fitting).

Table (3.9): Best ARX Model According to Accuracy Criteria after Bivariate Wavelet Filtering

Models	AIC	FPE	MSE	Fitting
ARX(10, 10, 8)	300.97	52.39	11.03	77.39
ARX(9,10,8)	305.42	55.99	12.69	75.75
ARX(8,10,8)	311.71	62.47	15.20	73.46
ARX(8,9,8)	319.08	70.05	19.46	69.97
ARX(8,8,8)	329.14	84.04	26.41	65.01
ARX(10,5,8)	337.17	101.81	30.11	62.64
ARX(10,4,8)	336.13	97.84	30.75	62.24
ARX(9,4,8)	333.90	90.54	31.96	61.51
ARX(8,4,8)	332.85	86.48	34.07	60.26
ARX(9,2,10)	334.67	89.97	35.44	59.46

Based on the model identification results, seen in Table 3.9, best ARX model is ARX (10,10,8) with a fitting percentage criterion equals to 77.39%, MSE: 11.03, FPE: 52.39, and AIC: 300.97.

Therefore, after estimating the parameters of the ARX(10, 10, 8) model through MATLAB, it could be written as presented in the following formula:

$$\phi(B)y_t = \psi(B)x_t + \epsilon_t$$

where: $\phi(B) = 1 - 0.6288B - 0.3186B^2 + 0.278B^3 + 0.3661B^4 - 0.3176B^5 - 0.7228B^6 + 0.5012B^7 + 1.058B^8 - 0.7302B^9 + 0.3623B^{10}$

and

$$\psi(B) = 3.123B^8 - 1.773B^9 - 1.183B^{10} + 0.6994B^{11} + 0.7898B^{12} - 0.6128B^{13} - 0.4608B^{14} + 0.438B^{15} + 3.285B^{16} - 1.955B^{17}$$

Among more than **30,000** different ARX models with bivariate wavelets filtering, the researcher arrived to the above selected model which is the best model.

The selected ARX model has a random residuals and uncorrelated residual values with the exogenous input variable, as presented in figure 3.9 and 3.10.

Figure (3.9): Error's Autocorrelation for ARX(10, 10, 8) Model

Figure (3.10): Cross-Correlation Errors for ARX(10,10,8) Model with of Input Variable

It is clear from Figure 3.9 that the autocorrelation values within the confidence intervals, and also Figure 3.10 describes the cross-correlation of these residuals with the input variable. Both correlations are within acceptable intervals.

Now, it is possible to test the error term with wavelet filtering for normality test, as seen in table 3.10:

H₀: The Errors with Wavelet Filtering follows a normal distribution

H₁: The Errors with Wavelet Filtering does not follow a normal distribution

Table (3.10): Test of Normality for Errors with Wavelet Filtering

Details	Different Kinds of Normality Test (Goodness of Fit Test)					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Anderson-Darling		Chi-Squared	
Statistic	0.09253		0.81996		0.38443	
P-Value	0.7918		Not Available		0.94344	
α	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.05	0.01
Critical Value	0.19625	0.23544	2.5018	3.9074	7.8147	11.345
Reject H₀?	No	No	No	No	No	No

Table 3.10 shows the normality test for it using 3 goodness of fit tests: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Anderson-Darling test, and Chi-Squared test. It appears from all these tests that the error is distributed normally at $\alpha = 0.01$.

6.5 Forecasting Performance

All the previous sections had been done in order to discover an appropriate ARX model for the time series data. But the process is not finishing at this point but last step remained which is related to forecasting of output data. After model identification and validation is executed, the forecast for crude oil prices with the help of production input series are presented in Table 3.11. It shows the forecasting of the OPEC prices through two identified ARX models with and without bivariate models.

Table (3.11): Forecasting of Crude Oil prices of OPEC Organization through Determined Dynamic Models

Year	ARX(10 10 6) without Wavelet Filtering	ARX(10 10 8) with Haar Wavelet Filtering
2019	92.77	68.37
2020	68.01	59.20

From comparison of the above 2 models and looking at the accuracy criteria in table 3.12, concluding that the proposed new forecasting ARX model with bivariate wavelet filtering is better than classical ARX model and even the forecasting values in for 2019 and 2020 in the proposed model are better than classical ARX model.

Table (3.12): Accuracy Criteria Comparison between Classical and Proposed Dynamic models (with and without Bivariate Wavelet Filtering)

Models	Models	AIC	FPE	MSE	Fitting
Classical ARX Model	ARX(10, 10, 6)	353.18	163.00	34.32	70.22
Proposed New Model	ARX(10, 10, 8)	300.97	52.39	11.03	77.39

Finally, the thesis analyses and forecasting had been completed and must be transferred to conclusions and recommendations that will be discussed in the next chapter. In the next chapter, the most important findings will be mentioned and highlighted.

CHAPTER FOUR
(CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS)

CHAPTER FOUR

7.1 Introduction

Depending on the results of previous chapters that are summarized and evaluated, the conclusions are presented, possible enhancements are suggested and some ideas regarding further work are recommended in this chapter.

7.2 Conclusions

Based on the main results given by chapter three, the following major conclusions are drawn:

1. The ARX model was successfully benefited from bivariate wavelet filtering, thus, the proposed ARX model is more powerful than the classical ARX model.
2. The forecasts of crude oil prices in the next two years using proposed model were more appropriate than classical models.
3. It appeared that detrending was better than differencing to convert applied time series data to stationary when using bivariate wavelet filtering.
4. It is concluded from the estimated model that the average crude oil prices in 2020 will be fairly less than 2019.

7.3 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions given in previous section, the following major recommendations are drawn:

1. Strongly recommending OPEC administration and related institutes to use the proposed forecasting model for crude oil prices.

2. Applying other input exogenous variables that have effects on crude oil prices of OPEC Organization rather than crude oil production.
3. Applying other kinds of dynamic systems in forecasting multiple time series data, such as ARIMAX, BJ, and Output Error methods, and comparing them with filtering models using Haar wavelets.
4. Applying other kinds of linear and nonlinear dynamic systems in forecasting multiple time series data.
5. Since the proposed method was better than classical methods, it is recommended to apply multivariate dynamic systems with multivariate wavelet filtering.

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